

Synthesis of some Newer Thiazolo and Thiadiazino Derivatives from 6-Methyl- or 6-Nitro-2,3-dichloroquinoxalines

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Interaction of 6-methyl- or 6-nitro-2,3-dichloroquinoxaline (1a, b) with thiourea in ethanol led to the formation of diquinoxalino[2,3-b : 2',3'-e]-1,4-dithien derivatives (2a, b) with 2-imino-2,3-dihydrothiazolo[4,5-b]quinoxalines (3a, b). 7-Methyl- or 7-nitro-3-amino-2-imino-2,3-dihydrothiazolo[4,5-b]quinoxaline (6a, b) were prepared and reacted with acid chlorides and aldehydes to give 7-9. Also interaction of 6a, b with carbon disulphide gave the corresponding 2-mercaptothiadiazine[5,6-b]quinoxaline derivatives (11a, b). Condensation of 11a, b with hydrazine hydrate gave 13c, d which were cyclised with acetic anhydride and benzoyl chloride to give 15a-d.

SAIKACHI and Tagami¹ prepared thiazolo[4,5-b]-quinoxaline ring system by reacting 2-mercapto-3-aminoquinoxaline with acid chlorides. In another publication the above system was synthesised by the interaction between 2,3-dichloroquinoxaline and N-substituted-thiourea². Recently, the latter method was used through interaction of 2,3-dichloroquinoxaline with thiourea³. Since the thiourea molecule has a several nucleophilic centers⁴⁻⁶, the reaction between thiourea and dichloroquinoxaline leads to the possibility⁷ of the formation of several products. The experiments showed that this reaction is depended on the type of solvent employed.

In view of these observations, it was considered of interest to synthesise some new quinoxaline analogues of 7-methyl- or 7-nitrothiazolo[4,5-b]-quinoxalines and 8-methyl- or 8-nitrothiadiazino[5,6-b]quinoxalines.

1
1a; R=CH₃,
1b; R=NO₂

Thus interaction of 6-methyl- or 6-nitro-2,3-dichloroquinoxaline (1a or b) with thiourea in DMSO furnished diquinoxalino[2,3-b : 2',3'-e]-1,4-dithien derivatives (2a, b). On repeating this reaction using ethanol as solvent, 2-imino-2,3-dihydrothiazolo[4,5-b]quinoxaline derivatives (3a, b) were formed together with 2a, b.

2
2a; R=CH₃,
2b; R=NO₂

3
3a; R=CH₃,
3b; R=NO₂

These compounds (3) can exist in the imino or the amino form or in both the forms. Attempted preparation of the diazonium salts or Schiff bases from compounds 3 failed which demonstrated our tautomeric structure.

Acetylation or sulphonylation of the iminothiazoloquinoxaline (3a, b) took place at position-2 and furnished 2-acetylamino- or sulphonylaminothiazoloquinoxaline (4a-c).

4
4a; R₁=CH₃, R₂=COOH,
4b; R₁=CH₃, R₂=O₂SO₂H,
4c; R₁=NO₂, R₂=COOH

Interaction of 6-methyl- or 6-nitro-2,3-dichloroquinoxalines (1a, b) with acetone thiosemicarbazone in ethanol gave 7-methyl- or 7-nitro-3-amino-2-imino-2,3-dihydrothiazolo[4,5-b]quinoxaline hydrochlorides (5a, b). The free bases (6a, b) were released from 5a,b through the decomposition with either sodium hydroxide (10%) or sodium acetate (10%) solutions. The free base (6) could be converted back to its hydrochloride (5) by the action of concentrated HCl/HCl(gas). An important test for the structure confirmation of 6 was to deaminate it using nitrous acid⁸ to give 2-imino-2,3-dihydrothiazolo[4,5-b]quinoxalines (3).

5
5a; R=CH₃,
5b; R=NO₂

6
6a; R=CH₃,
6b; R=NO₂

Acetylation of **6a,b** with acetyl chloride or acetic anhydride gave the corresponding triacetyl derivatives (**7a, b**).

7
7a; R=OH,
7b; R=NO₂

8
8a; R=OH, Ar=C₆H₅,
8b; R=OH, Ar=C₆H₄, Cl-*p*
8c; R=NO₂, Ar=C₆H₅

The free bases (**6a, b**) undergo cyclisation with benzoyl chloride or *p*-chlorobenzoyl chloride to give triazolo(3',2':2,3)-thiazolo[4,5-*b*]quinoxaline derivatives (**8a-c**).

The Schiff bases 3-arylideneimino-2-imino-2,3-dihydrothiazolo[4,5-*b*]quinoxalines (**9a-d**) were obtained by the condensation of the free bases (**6a, b**) with aromatic aldehydes. The imino group in the Schiff base (**9a**) was acetylated with acetyl chloride to give the acetyl derivative (**10**).

9
9a; R=OH, Ar=C₆H₅,
9b; R=OH, Ar=C₆H₄, Cl-*p*
9c; R=NO₂, Ar=C₆H₅,
9d; R=NO₂, Ar=C₆H₄, NO₂-*o*

10

It was found that treatment of 3-amino-2,3-dihydrothiazolo[4,5-*b*]quinoxaline with carbon disulphide caused ring expansion with the formation of 2-mercapto-4*H*-1,3,4-thiadiazino[5,6-*b*]quinoxaline⁷. Thus, interaction of the free amino derivatives (**6a, b**) with carbon disulphide in pyridine or sodium hydroxide afforded 8-methyl- or 8-nitro-2-mercapto-4*H*-1,3,4-thiadiazino[5,6-*b*]quinoxaline (**11a, b**) which can exist in two tautomeric forms.

11
11a; R=OH,
11b; R=NO₂

Methylation of **11a,b** with dimethyl sulphate produced the corresponding 8-methyl- or 8-nitro-2-methylmercapto-4-methylthiadiazinoquinoxaline (**12a, b**).

12
12a; R=OH,
12b; R=NO₂

13
13a; R=OH, R'=CH₂C₆H₅,
13b; R=NO₂, R'=CH₂C₆H₅,
13c; R=OH, R'=NH₂,
13d; R=NO₂, R'=NH₂

Interaction of **11a,b** with benzylamine or hydrazine hydrate gave the corresponding (2-benzylamino or hydrazino)-4*H*-1,3,4-thiadiazino[5,6-*b*]quinoxaline derivatives (**13a-d**). Condensation of **13c,d** with benzaldehyde or *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde gave the corresponding 2-hydrazono-1,3,4-thiadiazino[5,6-*b*]quinoxaline derivatives (**14a-d**).

14
14a; R=CH₃, Ar=C₆H₅,
14b; R=CH₃, Ar=C₆H₄, Cl-*p*
14c; R=NO₂, Ar=C₆H₅,
14d; R=NO₂, Ar=C₆H₄, Cl-*p*

15
15a; R=CH₃, R'=OH,
15b; R=CH₃, R'=C₆H₅,
15c; R=NO₂, R'=CH₃,
15d; R=NO₂, R'=C₆H₅

Cyclisation of **13c,d** could be effected by acetic anhydride or benzoyl chloride to give the corresponding triazolo[3',2':2,3]-1,3,4-thiadiazino[5,6-*b*]quinoxaline derivatives (**15a-d**).

Experimental

Melting points were determined on an electrothermal melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. Microanalyses were carried out at Microanalytical Unit, Cairo University on a Heraeus instrument by using rate of oxygen method and benzoic acid as standard. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on Pye-Unicam Sp. 1200 and Sp. 1000 spectrophotometers and nmr spectra on a Varian EM-350 L, 60 MHz spectrometer using TMS as internal standard.

Diquinoxalino[2,3-*b*:2',3'-*e*]-1,4-dithien derivatives (**2a,b**): Method (a): Thiourea (0.01 mol) was added to a solution of **1a,b** (0.01 mol) in DMSO (50 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 6 h. The resulting solid was recrystallised from the proper solvent to give **2a,b** (Table 1). Method (b): Thiourea (0.01 mol) was added to a suspension of **1a,b** (0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 30 min. The resulting solid was recrystallised to give the dithien derivatives of type **2a, b**. The products obtained by method (a) were found to be identical with that obtained by method (b). However, the products obtained by method (a) have lower yields than that by method (b); $\nu_{\max}$ 1530 (CN) and 750 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C).

7-Methyl- and 7-nitro-2,3-dihydrothiazolo[4,5-*b*]quinoxaline (**3a,b**). Method (a): The filtrate from method (b) in the preparation of **2a,b**, was poured into water (100 ml) and the resulting solid was recrystallised to give **3a,b** (Table 1). Method (b): NaNO₂ solution (5*N*; 100 ml) was added dropwise to a solution of **6a, b** (0.02 mol) in concentrated HCl (75 ml) at -5° to 0° during 2-3 h. The reaction mixture was left to stand at room temperature for 2 h with occasional shaking and then added to crushed ice (100 g). The resulting solid was recrystallised to give **3a, b**.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	M.p.** °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
2a	340 ^b	65	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₄ S ₂
2b	325 ^b	70	C ₁₆ H ₈ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂
3a	232 ^c	65	C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₄ S
3b	317 ^a	60	C ₉ H ₈ N ₄ O ₂ S
4a	318 ^d	62	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₄ OS
4b	270 ^d	64	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂
4c	396 ^c	68	C ₁₁ H ₇ N ₄ O ₂ S
5a	340 ^a	76	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₄ SOCl
5b	320 ^d	75	C ₉ H ₇ N ₄ SO ₂ Cl
6a	315 ^c	68	C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₄ S
6b	225 ^c	72	C ₉ H ₈ N ₄ SO ₂
7a	196 ^c	75	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ S
7b	226 ^a	72	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ S
8a	186 ^d	75	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₄ S
8b	255 ^c	77	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ N ₄ SOCl
8c	308 ^b	78	C ₁₆ H ₈ N ₄ O ₂ S
9a	238 ^c	78	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₄ S
9b	248 ^c	76	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₄ OS
9c	231 ^a	83	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₂ S
9d	229 ^a	86	C ₁₆ H ₈ N ₄ O ₄ S
10	222 ^c	80	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ N ₄ OS
11a	350 ^a	70	C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₄ S ₂
11b	340 ^a	69	C ₉ H ₈ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂
12a	116 ^c	75	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₄ S ₂
12b	307 ^c	72	C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂
13a	251 ^c	70	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₄ S
13b	260 ^d	68	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ S
13c	334 ^b	75	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₄ S
13d	357 ^a	66	C ₉ H ₇ N ₄ O ₂ S
14a	240 ^d	69	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₄ S
14b	325 ^d	71	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₄ SOCl
14c	280 ^d	75	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₄ SO ₂
14d	320 ^d	68	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₄ SO ₂ Cl
15a	311 ^d	75	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₄ S
15b	317 ^b	80	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₄ S
15c	340 ^d	70	C ₁₁ H ₇ N ₄ O ₂ S
15d	355 ^b	75	C ₁₆ H ₈ N ₄ O ₂ S

*C, H and N analyses found satisfactory. **Solvent of crystallisation: ^aacetic acid, ^bdimethyl formamide-water, ^cbenzene, ^dethanol.

Ir spectra showed a very wide absorption band at 3 600–2 600 cm⁻¹ since in the solid state the hydrogen atom in 3-position is intramolecularly associated with the nitrogen atoms of quinoxaline ring system, and at 1 630 cm⁻¹ (CN). ¹H nmr spectra (CD₂COCD₂) of 3a showed peaks at δ 2.58 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.88 (2H, broad hump, NH disappeared on deuteration) and 7.4–7.8 (3H, m, ArH).

Acetylation of 3a: A solution of 3a (0.01 mol) in acetic anhydride (15 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. The cold solution was then poured into crushed ice (100 g) to give 4a (Table 1); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 050 (NH) and 1 700 cm⁻¹ (CO).

Interaction of 3a,b with benzene sulphonyl chloride: A mixture of 3a,b (0.01 mol) and benzene sulphonyl chloride (0.01 mol) in pyridine (20 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. The resulting solid was recrystallised to give 4b,c (Table 1); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 120 (NH), 1 340 and 1 150 cm⁻¹ (SO₂N asym. and sym.).

7-Methyl- and 7-nitro-3-amino-2-imino-2,3-dihydrothiazolo[4,5-b]quinoxaline hydrochloride (5a, b): Method (a): A mixture of 1a,b (0.01 mol) and acetone thiosemicarbazone (0.01 mol) in absolute ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 30 min. The

resulting solid was recrystallised to give 5a,b (Table 1). Method (b): The free base (6a,b; 0.01 mol) was treated with HCl/HCl gas to give 5a,b (m.p. and m.m.p.).

7-Methyl- and 7-nitro-3-amino-2-imino-2,3-dihydrothiazolo[4,5-b]quinoxaline (6a,b): The hydrochloride salt (5a,b) was treated with NaOH (10% excess) or sodium acetate solution (10% excess) at 50° for 1 h. The resulting solid was recrystallised from proper solvent to give the free bases (6a, b; Table 1); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 400, 3 300 (NH₂), 3 100 (NH) and 1 620 cm⁻¹ (C=N).

The triacetyl derivatives (6a, b): A solution of 6a, b (0.01 mol) in acetyl chloride (25 ml) or acetic anhydride (10 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and poured into crushed ice to give the triacetyl derivatives (7a, b; Table 1). Ir spectra showed the disappearance of both NH₂ and NH bands while the carbonyl bands appeared around 1 680–1 730 cm⁻¹. Mass spectrum of 7b showed a molecular ion peak at *m/e* 388 (11%), together with a base peak at *m/e* 42 (100%); other fragmentation ions appeared at *m/e* 331 (20%), 288 (40%), 260 (48%) and 231 (8%).

Triazolo[3',2']thiazolo[4,5-b]quinoxalines (8a–c): A solution of 6a,b (0.01 mol) in benzoyl chloride or *p*-chlorobenzoyl chloride (20 ml) was refluxed for 5 h. The resulting solid was recrystallised to give 8a–c (Table 1). Ir spectra showed the absence of both NH₂ and NH bands in the parent compound.

3-Arylideneimino-2-imino-2,3-dihydrothiazolo[4,5-b]quinoxalines (9a–d): A mixture of 6a, b (0.01 mol) and the appropriate aldehyde (0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. The resulting solid was recrystallised to give the corresponding Schiff bases (9a–d; Table 1); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 200 cm⁻¹ (NH).

7-Methyl-3-benzylidenetimino-2-acetylimino-2,3-dihydrothiazolo[4,5-b]quinoxaline (10): A solution of the Schiff base (9a; 0.01 mol) in acetyl chloride (20 ml) was refluxed for 2 h to give 10 (Table 1); $\nu_{\max}$ 1 750 cm⁻¹ (CO).

8-Methyl- and 8-nitro-2-mercapto-4H-1,3,4-thiadiazino[5:6-b]quinoxalines (11a, b): Method (a): Carbon disulphide (0.04 mol) was added to a solution of 6a, b (0.02 mol) in anhydrous pyridine (50 ml) and refluxed for 6 h with stirring to give 11a, b (Table 1). Method (b): Carbon disulphide (0.04 mol) was added dropwise to a solution of 6a, b (0.02 mol) in DMF (50 ml) and sodium hydroxide (5*N*; 20 ml), and then acidified with hydrochloric acid (till pH 2) to give 11a,b, (m.p., m.m.p.); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 140 (NH) and 1 620 cm⁻¹ (C=N).

Methylation of 11a, b: Dimethyl sulphate (0.04 mol) was added dropwise to a solution of 11a, b (0.02 mol) in sodium hydroxide solution (10%, 50 ml) and the reaction mixture was allowed to stand at 40° for 30 min. The resulting solid was recrystallised from suitable solvent to give 12a, b (Table 1).

Ir spectra showed the disappearance of NH band in the parent compound and the appearance of CH aliphatic band at 2990 cm^{-1} . Mass spectra of **12a** gave a molecular ion peak at m/e 276 (100%) together with the peaks at m/e 261 (10%), 243 (12%), 236 (11%), 215 (35%), 205 (30%), 186 (10%), 174 (9%), 165 (8%), 136 (17%), 115 (9%) and 77 (14%).

8-Methyl- and 8-nitro-2-benzylamino-4H-1,3,4-thiadiazino[5,6-b]quinoxalines (13a, b): A mixture of **11a, b** (0.01 mol) and benzylamine (0.02 mol excess) was refluxed for 6 h. The reaction mixture was then poured into crushed ice and acidified with dilute HCl to give **13a, b** (Table 1); $\nu_{\max}$ 3400, 3050 (two NH), 2980 (CH) and 1600 cm^{-1} (C=N); **13a** δ (CD_2COCD_2) 2.5(3H, s, CH_3), 3.1(2H, s, CH_2), 5.0 (2H, hump, 2NH which disappeared on deuteration), 7.4–7.8 (8H, m, ArH); m/e 321 (90%), base peak 262 (100%); 294, (16%), 288 (52%), 250 (18%), 218 (25%), 187 (38%), 174 (16%), 158 (40%), 143(28%), 129 (54%), 112 (20%) and 62 (88%).

8-Methyl- and 8-nitro-2-hydrazino-4H-1,3,4-thiadiazino[5 : 6-b]quinoxalines (13c, d): A mixture of **11a, b** (0.02 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (98%, 0.04 mol excess) was stirred at room temperature for 0.5 h. The resulting solid was recrystallised to give **13c, d** (Table 1); $\nu_{\max}$ 3400 (NH₂, NH) and 1600 cm^{-1} (CN).

Formation of the hydrazone derivatives (14a–b): A mixture of **13c, d** (0.02 mol) and benzaldehyde or *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde (0.02 mol) in ethanol (100 ml) was refluxed for 4 h to give **14a–d** (Table 1); $\nu_{\max}$ 3200 (two NH) and 1610 cm^{-1} (C=N).

Cyclisation of 13a, d: A solution of **13a, d** (0.02 mol) in acetic anhydride or benzoyl chloride (20 ml) was refluxed for 2 h to give the corresponding triazolo derivatives (**15a–d**; Table 1); ir spectra showed the absence of NH₂ and NH bands of both hydrazide and secondary amine from the parent compound.

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